

On Mixed Mode Fracture in Off-Axis Unidirectional Graphite-Epoxy Composites

A. S. D. Wang¹⁾, N. N. Kishore¹⁾, W. W. Feng²⁾

1) Department of Mechanical Engineering, Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA 19104, U.S.A.

2) Lawrence National Laboratory, Mail Stop 342, Livermore, CA 94550, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the results of a fracture experiment, in which matrix-dominant mixed-mode cracks are induced with controlled propagation direction and controlled values of mode-II to mode-I ratio. The test specimens used belong to a class of off-axis, doubly side-notched unidirectional graphite-epoxy composite. By varying the off-axis angle from 0° to 90° , a wide range of mixed-mode cracking conditions are created under a simple uniaxial tension. From the test results the mixed-mode material fracture toughness measured in terms of the critical energy release rate $G_{(I,II)c}$ is determined as a continuous function of G_{II}/G_I ratio.

INTRODUCTION

Many crack-like failures in continuous fiber composites and their laminates are contained within the interface planes where the matrix phase dominates the fracture responses. Transverse cracks, ply delamination and fiber splitting are examples of such failures that occur frequently in epoxy-based composites and laminates. From a macroscopic descriptive view point, the propagation modes of these cracks are more or less self-similar, being confined in a certain interface plane, although a microscopic examination of the individual crack surfaces may show distinctly different morphology from one type of crack to another.

Recent studies by Wang, Crossman, et. al. [1-4] have shown that methods of the classical fracture mechanics can be applied to model the initiation and the propagation of these cracking modes within the frame work of ply-elasticity (see, e.g. Tsai and Hahn [5]), i.e. the individual material layers in the laminate are considered homogeneous and anisotropic for purpose of stress analysis.

Generally speaking, self-similar mode-I cracks can be effectively described by a single criterion using either the critical stress intensity factor K_{Ic} , or the critical strain energy release rate G_{Ic} as a constant material fracture toughness parameter. However, owing to the actual heterogeneous nature of the material microstructure, values of K_{Ic} or G_{Ic} may differ greatly depending on the particular interface in which the crack is contained. Moreover, the crack surface morphology may also vary with the direction of crack propagation even though the crack is contained in the same interface[6,7]. Thus, precautions should be exercised in order for the classical fracture mechanics methods to apply at this level of macroscopic fracture analysis.

In the case of mixed-mode or shear-dominant cracks, there has been concern about the effects of matrix yielding in the vicinity of the crack-tip, which may influence greatly the material toughness values. Recent experiments on unidirectional graphite-epoxy composites have confirmed that the material critical energy release rate $G_{(I,II)c}$ obtained in a mixed-mode crack condition may be several times larger than G_{Ic} which is obtained under mode-I crack condition. For example Vanderkley[8] and Wilkins[9] found that $G_{(I,II)c}$ is more than 3.5 times larger than G_{Ic} at a G_{II}/G_I ratio of three; Jurf and Pipes[10] found it to be 9 times more than G_{Ic} under nearly a pure shear crack condition. The increased material toughness is thought to stem from matrix yielding under primarily shear. Thus, in a mixed-mode case, the value of $G_{(I,II)c}$ may actually depend on the ratio of G_{II}/G_I .

For cracks with crack-tip yielding of small dimensions, the energy balance criterion of Griffith[11] may still apply by virtue of the 'quasi-brittle' concept[12]. Then, an appropriately measured material toughness parameter is essential for any mixed-mode fracture criterion.

This paper discusses the results of an experiment in which matrix-dominant mixed-mode cracks are induced with controlled propagation directions and with controlled values of mode-II to mode-I ratio. The test specimens used belong to a class of off-axis, doubly side-notched unidirectional graphite-epoxy 8-ply laminates, see illustration in Fig. 1. By varying the off-axis angle θ from 0° to 90° , a wide range of mixed-mode cracking conditions are created under a simple uniaxial tension. Thus, from the test results the mixed-mode material fracture toughness measured in terms of the critical energy release rate $G_{(I,II)c}$ is determined as a continuous function of G_{II}/G_I ratio.

The present test results show that $G_{(I,II)c}$ is a monotonically increasing function of G_{II}/G_I , confirming the early finding reported in Refs.[8-10]. In addition, the present data also indicates a slight increase in G_{Ic} in mixed-mode crack conditions.

It should be emphasized that the present test results are far from conclusive; more refined experiment as well as analysis are needed.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The material used in the experiment is the T300/934 graphite-epoxy composite system. Test specimens are cut from 8-ply unidirectional laminates with off-axis angles from 0° to 90° at 15° intervals. Each of the test specimens has a width of 2.5 cm (1 inch) and a length of 23 cm (9 inch); aluminum tabs of 3.8 cm (1.5") in length are mounted onto each end of the specimen. Double side notches are introduced using an 8-mil (0.2 mm) diamond saw; the depth of the cut is 3.8 mm (0.15"). A general configuration of the test specimen is shown in Fig. 1.

Under uniaxial tension, a crack is initiated from the notch-tip and propagated along the fiber-matrix interface, the θ direction. Thus, for the seven θ angles from 0° to 90° , a class of matrix-dominant, mixed-mode cracks is experimentally obtained. The curve in Fig. 1 shows the critical far-field laminate stress $\bar{\sigma}_x$ at the onset of crack for each of the seven θ angles; the open circles denote the averaged value of four specimens while the vertical bars represent the scatter.

The mode-I and mode-II energy release rates G_I and G_{II} available at the notch-tip and along the crack growth path (the θ direction) are then calculated by a 2-dimensional, plane-stress finite element routine. The numerical routine incorporates a special crack growth simulation technique which calculates G_I and G_{II} as functions of the crack length a (for details, see Refs. [1,2]); the crack length a is measured from the notch-tip along the fiber (θ) direction.

Fig. 2 shows the calculated G_I and G_{II} as functions of the crack length a .^{*} Note that these functions are obtained by imposing a unit far-field laminate strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$, for strain-controlled loading conditions. Of course, $\bar{\epsilon}_x$ is related to $\bar{\sigma}_x$ by the laminate axial stiffness \bar{E}_x .

It is seen from the curves in Fig. 2 that the fracture events are essentially of mode-I for $\theta \geq 45^\circ$; but mode-II contribution increases rapidly as θ becomes smaller. Also, with increasing mode-II contribution, the energy release rates G_I and G_{II} display a peculiar behavior: that the value of the energy release rates is highest at the notch-tip, and it reduces somewhat as the crack grows away from the notch-tip. In fact, a minimum value exists at a certain finite crack size.

It is felt that the minimum available energy actually determines the onset of the finite crack which is observed experimentally. Thus, Fig. 3 shows the minimum values of G_I and G_{II} for each of the θ angles. From Fig. 3 the ratio of G_{II}/G_I is plotted also as a function of θ , Fig. 4.

Now, assume in each case tested experimentally that onset of crack occurs when the total energy release rate $G_{(I,II)} = G_I + G_{II}$ reaches a certain critical value $G_{(I,II)c}$:

^{*} The material constants used in the calculation are given in Ref. [2].

$$G_I + G_{II} = G_{(I,II)c} \quad (1)$$

Since G_I and G_{II} are expressed in terms of the critical far-field strain $\bar{\epsilon}_x$, which is known experimentally, the mixed-mode critical energy release rate $G_{(I,II)c}$ is then determined as a function of G_{II}/G_I ratio, which is shown in Fig. 5.

From the results shown in Fig. 5, it is seen that for $\theta > 45^\circ$ the fracture mode is predominantly of mode-I; and

$$G_{(I,II)c} = G_{Ic} = 157 \text{ J/m}^2 \text{ (0.9 in/lb)} \quad (2)$$

This value agrees with those obtained by Cullen[6] and Williams[7] who used the AS-3501-02 graphite-epoxy system and tested under pure mode-I conditions.

At θ angles smaller than 45° , increased mode-II influence on the value of $G_{(I,II)c}$ is displayed by the curve in Fig. 5. The values of $G_{(I,II)c}$ agree with those obtained by Vanderkley[8] and Wilkins[9] who used the AS-3501-06 graphite-epoxy system. It is conceivable that by extrapolation of the $G_{(I,II)c}$ curve to the infinite value of G_{II}/G_I , a G_{IIc} may be obtained; and that value may reach such a magnitude as found by Jurf and Pipes[10].

Clearly, the problem of mixed-mode crack mechanisms is much more complicated than the limited experimental results have indicated in this paper. Continued efforts are needed, both experimentally and analytically.

Acknowledgement : The authors, A.S.D. Wang and N.N. Kishore, acknowledge the generous support received during the course of research from the Air Force Office of Scientific Research, Washington, D. C.

REFERENCE

- [1] Wang, A.S.D. and Crossman, F.W., 'Initiation and Growth of Transverse Cracks and Edge Delamination in Composite Laminates. Part 1, An Energy Method,' J. Composite Materials, Vol. 14(1980), pp. 71-87.
- [2] Crossman, F.W., Warren, W.J., Wang, A.S.D. and Law, G.E., 'Initiation and Growth of Transverse Cracks and Edge Delamination in Composite Laminates, Part 2, Experimental Correlation', J. Composite Materials, Vol. 14(1980), pp. 88-106.
- [3] Wang, A.S.D., 'Growth Mechanisms of Transverse Cracks and Ply Delamination in Composite Laminates', in Advances in Composite Materials, Proc. ICCM-III, 1980, pp. 170-182.
- [4] Wang, A.S.D. and Crossman, F.W., 'Fracture Mechanics of Transverse Cracks and Edge Delamination in Graphite-Epoxy Composite Laminates', Final Tech. Report, AFOSR F 49620-79-C-0206(1982).
- [5] Tsai, S.W. and Hahn, H.T., 'Introduction to Composite Materials' Technomics

Inc., Westport Conn.(1980).

- [6] Cullen, J.S., 'Mode-I Delamination of Unidirectional Graphite-Epoxy composite Under Complex Load Histories', Thesis, Texas A & M University(1981).
- [7] Williams, D., 'Mode-I Transverse Cracking in An Epoxy and A Graphite Fiber Reinforced Epoxy', Thesis, Texas A & M University(1981).
- [8] Vanderkley, P.S., 'Mode-I and Mode-II Delamination Fracture Toughness of A Unidirectional Graphite-Epoxy Composite', Thesis, Texas A & M Univ,(1981).
- [9] Wilkins, D.J., "A Comparison of the Delamination and Environmental Resistance of A Graphite-Epoxy and A Graphite-Bismaleimide", NAV-GD-0037, Naval Air System Command(1981).
- [10] Jurf, R.A. and Pipes, R.B., 'Interlaminar Fracture of Composite Material', Tech. Report, University of Delaware(1982).
- [11] Griffith, A.A., 'The Phenomena of Rupture and Flow in Solids', Phil. Trans. Roy. Soc., Vol. A221(1920), p.163.
- [12] Orowan, E.O., 'Fundamentals of Brittle Behavior of Metals', in Fatigue and Fracture of Metals, W.M. Murry, Ed. Wiley, N.Y.(1950), p.139.

Fig. 1 Far Field Laminate Stress At Onset Of Notch-Tip Crack

Fig. 2(a) Mode-I Energy Release Rate $G_I(a)$ for Various Off-axis Angles. (for $\bar{e}_x = 1.0$)

Fig. 2(b) Mode-II Energy Release Rate $G_{II}(a)$ for Various Off-Axis Angles. (for $\bar{e}_x = 1.0$)

Fig. 3 Calculated G_I and G_{II} At Various Off-Axis Angles.
(for $\bar{e}_x = 1.0$)

Fig. 4 Calculated G_{II}/G_I Ratio At Various Off-Axis Angles.
(for $\bar{e}_x = 1.0$)

Fig. 5 Critical Mixed-Mode Energy Release Rate $G_{(I,II)c}$
As A Function Of G_{II}/G_I Ratio.